

RATE-DEPENDENT UNDRAINED SHEAR BEHAVIOUR OF A COMPACTED LATERITIC SOIL

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ABSTRACT

Triaxial compression tests were carried out to evaluate the effect of strain rate on the undrained shear behaviour of compacted lateritic soil. Nine strain rates ranging between 0.5%/minute and 10.0%/minute were used. Stress paths to failure generally increased at higher strain rate, although there are some deviations from this trend. Brittleness index (defined as $I_B = (q_f/q_u) - 1$; where I_B is brittleness index, q_f is failure principal stress difference and q_u is ultimate principal stress difference) increased as strain rate increased indicating that increased strain rate reduces the ductility of compacted lateritic soil.

KEYWORDS: Compacted soil, Brittleness, Ductility, Lateritic soil, Strain rate, Stress path, Triaxial tests.

INTRODUCTION

The undrained stress-deformation behaviour of clays is significantly affected by a number of factors including the loading rate or strain rate. The influence of strain rate on the shear behaviour of clay soils has been studied in the past by several investigators (Casagrande and Wilson 1951; Richardson and Whitman 1963; Sheahan *et al.* 1996). These experimental studies were conducted on non-tropical soils. The results from these experiments show that the strength of the soils increases with increase in the rate of loading (Katti *et al.* 2003). Nwaiwu (1994) has shown that increased rate of loading resulted in increase in the strength of a compacted lateritic soil. However it is necessary to show the effect of strain-rate on the stress path to failure and ductility of compacted lateritic soil.

In order to provide information that will help in obtaining clear understanding of the strain rate effect on stress path to failure and ductility of lateritic soil, a series of laboratory tests were carried out to define the response of such material under triaxial loading. A total of nine (9) undrained triaxial compression tests were carried out on lateritic soil samples compacted at the optimum moisture content using the energy of the British Standard (BS) light compaction. The strain rates used in this study were 0.5, 0.67, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.33, 5.0, 10.0 %/min.

The results of the tests were used to show the behaviour of undisturbed lateritic soil at 2% minute strain rate as well as compacted lateritic soil specimens at varying strain rates. In general, increased strain rate caused increase in maximum principal stress difference, stress-strain modulus at failure, as well as stress path to failure and brittleness index. The increased brittleness index represents decreases in ductility of the compacted soil samples.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The soil sample used in this study, derived from coastal plain sands and alluvium of the Southern Tertiary to Quaternary sedimentary deposits, was obtained from an excavation at a depth of 2.0 to 2.15 metres below the original level of the lateritic soil deposit in the Ojota area of Lagos State, Southern Nigeria. The area is located in the tropical rain forest belt.

The Ojota laterite is mottled and is reddish in colour with patches of yellowish to brownish inclusions. The soil is loose becoming firm or dense with occasional fragments of sandstone. The soil is classified as inorganic clay of medium plasticity based on Casagrande's plasticity chart and/or clay of low plasticity (CL) according to the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS). The natural moisture content (w_n) is 17.6% and specific gravity of solids (G_s) is 2.63. The soil is made up of 38.3% fines and 61.7% sand, with a mean size (D_{50}) of 0.24 mm. The Atterberg limits of the material passing No. 40 sieve were obtained as follows: Liquid limit (w_l), 49.7%; plastic limit (w_p), 25%; plasticity index (PI), 24.7% and linear shrinkage, (LS), 9.4%.

Preparation and Testing of Specimens

The samples were prepared by oven drying at 105°C for 24 h and compacted at optimum moisture content of 18.7% using the energy of the standard Proctor compaction.

Three test specimens were extended from the mould immediately after each compaction. Using the split mould and later the membrane stretcher, individual test specimens, 38.1 mm in diameter and 76.2 mm in height were trimmed from the specimens extruded. Test specimens were wrapped in plastic bags and left over night in an airtight container in order to prevent moisture loss and to achieve a near uniform moisture distribution within the individual soil specimens.

Unconsolidated – undrained tests were performed in the standard 38.1mm diameter triaxial cell, without the measurement of pore water pressure. Specimens of the undisturbed lateritic soil were first tested at 2%/min strain-rate. All tests on compacted specimens were carried out with controlled strain at the optimum moisture content. Nine strain rates used ranged between 0.5%/min.and 10%/min All stress-strain curves were corrected for area changes using the procedure detailed in BS 1377 (1990).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Undrained Shear Behaviour of Undisturbed Lateritic Soil

The mean total stress, p and principal stress difference, q (p - q) diagram representing the stress path for the undisturbed lateritic soil is shown in Fig. 1a. A straight line was obtained for the total stress path. This is similar to the results obtained by Vanapalli *et al* (1996) for a glacial till as well as those reported by Lu and Likos (2006) for clayey soil types, under total stress conditions.

Fig. 1a Mean principal stress difference versus mean total stress at 2.0%/minute strain rate for undisturbed lateritic soil

Fig. 1b Brittleness index versus confining pressure at 2.0%/minute strain rate for undisturbed lateritic soil

The ductility of the undisturbed lateritic soil specimens was also estimated. And absolute measure of ductility behaviour is provided by the brittleness index (I_B) defined by the expression (Consoli *et al.* 1998):

$$(1)$$

where q_f and q_u are, respectively, the failure and ultimate principal stress differences or deviatoric stresses. Failure behaviour is said to become increasingly ductile as the index decreases, approaching zero. The brittleness index ranged between 2.14×10^{-2} and 2.68×10^{-2} (or 2.14% and 2.68%) as shown in Fig. 1b. The highest brittleness index value of 2.68×10^{-2} was obtained at a confining pressure of 200 kN/m².

Fig. 2 Mean principal stress difference versus mean total stress at different strain rates for compacted lateritic soil

Fig. 3 Brittleness index versus strain rate for compacted lateritic soil

Effects of Strain-Rate on Stress Path and Ductility

The effect of strain-rate on the total stress path shown in the $p - q$ space is given in Fig. 2. Different stress paths are obtained for different strain rates although the pattern in the stress paths did not follow the sequence of strain rate increases. Generally stress path for undrained loading tend to follow straight lines. In Fig. 2, there are clear deviations from the straight line stress path. This may be attributed to minor differences in microstructure. The plotting points in the stress paths are aligned at an angle of about 55° while the straight lines are inclined at angles less than 30°

The modulus of soil for undrained loading is usually a convenient way to characterize the stress-strain behaviour of a soil. Stress-strain behaviour of a soil, in turn, is very dependent on the stress path (Lambe and Whitman, 1979). It is expected that stress path to failure will be affected by strain rate as undrained modulus and hence stress-strain characteristics are affected by strain rate.

The ductility of the compacted lateritic soil specimens represented by the brittleness index is affected by strain rate. The brittleness index, defined in equation (1), generally increased up to a strain rate of 5%/minute (Fig.3).

Brittleness index values ranged between 0.0 and 0.13, but were generally less than 0.1 (10%). Increase in brittleness index corresponds to decrease in ductility. It is clearly seen that at higher strain rates ductility decreases. Increased strain rate caused the apparently ductile lateritic soil to fail in a brittle manner. This trend is in agreement with the behaviour of non-earth materials as indicated by Jastrzebski (1977)

CONCLUSION

Some aspects of the undrained shear behaviour of compacted lateritic soil at varying strain rates have been investigated. The following observations and conclusions are made regarding the rate-dependent shear behaviour of compacted lateritic soil:

1. Stress path to failure generally increased as strain rate increased. The inclinations of the straight line stress paths occur at angles less than 30° with respect to the horizontal. The plotting points for the stress paths formed defined patterns with inclinations of about 55° to the horizontal.
2. Ductility of the compacted lateritic soil specimens decreased at higher strain rates. Brittleness index was used as an absolute measure of ductility. Increase in brittleness index represented decrease in ductility. Brittleness index values ranged between 0.0 and 0.13 (or 0% and 13%).

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